

The Current State of Corporate Voice of the Consumer Programs: A Study of Organizational
Listening Practices and Effectiveness

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The author wishes to thank Cynthia Grimm of CX Solutions for insights that helped shape the design and execution of the research reported in this article.

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Abstract

While there is a rich literature on listening in interpersonal settings, studies of organizational listening have been comparatively scarce. A growing body of recent research, however, underscores the importance of how effectively (or poorly) organizations listen and attempt to respond to their respective publics and external stakeholders.

This paper describes research focusing on organizational practices and effectiveness related to capturing, analyzing, disseminating, and utilizing the “Voice of the Consumer.” After reviewing literature regarding factors that may shape and influence Voice of the Consumer (VoC) program effectiveness, the paper describes a two-phased program of research aimed at: (a) identifying specific characteristics and practices that can/should be used to describe VoC programs, and (b) assessing the current state of VoC programs with respect to overall effectiveness, and in relation to the preceding specific characteristics and practices. Results reveal that a majority of organizations have not yet achieved a desired level of VoC program effectiveness, and that most are better at capturing consumer feedback than they are at analyzing, disseminating, or utilizing it to improve products, services, and consumer experiences. Implications for theory-building and knowledge development, along with practical implications for organizational planning and management, are discussed.

Keywords: Organizational Listening; Voice of the Consumer; Corporate Communication;

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Organizations in both public and private sectors increasingly are attempting to capture – and leverage insights drawn from – the “Voice of the Consumer.” More and more organizations are conducting surveys and focus groups, soliciting comments and complaints, recording consumer calls, scouring social media, and gathering consumer feedback from a variety of other sources. Schmidt-Subramanian (2014) reports that nearly 60% of North American companies have implemented formalized Voice of the Consumer (VoC) programs, and Temkin (2016) reports that spending on VoC programs is increasing.

Investments in VoC programs typically are justified on the grounds that insights drawn from VoC sources enable organizations to “set the agenda” for improving products, services, and consumer experiences/relationships. Indeed, empirical support for anticipated benefits of consumer listening includes improved ability to identify emerging consumer needs that serve as the basis for new product development (Urban & Hauser, 2004), increased likelihood of consumer retention and engagement (de Ruyter & Wetzels, 2000), heightened willingness of consumers to share both positive and negative feedback (Beatty, Reynolds, Noble, & Harrison, 2012), increased effectiveness at handling consumer problems and complaints (Bolkan & Daly, 2009; Bolkan, Goodboy, & Bachman, 2012; Davidow, 2003), increased likelihood that consumers will engage with organizational media and messaging (Hong & Yang, 2011), and improved effectiveness at participating in and shaping “brand conversations” taking place via social media (Blackshaw, 2008; Godes & Mayzlin, 2009; Graham & Havlena, 2007). Conversely, ineffectiveness at and/or unwillingness to engage in consumer listening has been shown to be a major reason for consumer defections (Pepitone, 2011).

Investments in VoC programs also often are justified on the grounds that they contribute to market performance and achievement of desired business results. Several studies have shown how organizations that are good at listening to consumers – and responding in meaningful, substantive ways – perform more effectively in the marketplace than their competitors (Hult & Ketchen, 2001; Jaworski & Kohli 1993; Johnston & Reed, 2017; Morgan, Vorhies, & Mason, 2009).

Commercial goals and self-interest are not the only reasons organizations invest in VoC programs. Many VoC programs are implemented in response to growing demand for corporate responsibility, transparency, and social equity. Consumer consciousness is ever-increasing, requiring firms to pursue continually a balance between their own and consumer interests, and to demonstrate sensitivity to this balance in all aspects of organizational conduct (Blackshaw, 2008; Brandt, 2015; Sifry, 2011; Tapscott & Ticoll, 2012). Such balance is difficult to achieve unless consumer voices are represented, assimilated, and addressed via organizational media, messaging, decisions, and actions.

Thus, it is clear that organizations increasingly are investing in VoC programs, and it is also clear why. However, what remains is a question of VoC program efficacy: *How effective are organizational efforts to capture and leverage the Voice of the Consumer?*

This paper describes a recent research project, involving North American companies, focusing on organizational practices and effectiveness related to capturing, analyzing, disseminating, and utilizing the Voice of the Consumer. After reviewing the literature regarding factors that may shape and influence VoC program effectiveness, the paper describes a two-phased program of research aimed at: (a) identifying specific characteristics and practices that can/should be used to describe VoC programs, and (b) assessing the current state of VoC

programs with respect to overall effectiveness, and in relation to the preceding specific characteristics and practices. Key findings are presented, including specific methods used by organizations to listen to consumers, and managerial perceptions of overall VoC program effectiveness, as well as specific VoC program strengths and weaknesses. Implications for theory-building and knowledge development, practical implications for organizational planning and management, limitations of this study, and directions for future research subsequently are discussed.

Factors Influencing VoC Program Design and Effectiveness

What does it take to build a successful Voice of the Consumer program? What are the keys to VoC program effectiveness?

Attempts to capture and leverage the Voice of the Consumer can be thought of as a special form of *organizational listening*. Macnamara (2016) defines organizational listening as the approach and methods “applied by an organization to give recognition, acknowledgement, attention, interpretation, understanding, consideration, and response to its stakeholders and publics” (p. 52). Macnamara (2018) argues that effectiveness at organizational listening “requires and depends” on the creation of an “architecture of listening” comprised of multiple elements. These elements include: (a) an organizational *culture* that promotes listening; (b) *policies* that specify and require listening; (c) *systems* and *technologies* that are open, interactive, and that aid listening; (d) *resources* and staff to ‘do the work’ of listening; (e) *skills* for listening; and (f) *articulation* of the voices of stakeholders and publics to organizational decision making and action. All of these elements are required, says Macnamara, to address factors that make organizational listening particularly challenging, including: (a) the asynchronous nature of organizational listening; (b) the fact that such listening usually is mediated and delegated to

specific organizational functions, departments, and/or individual members; and (c) the necessity of “scaling up” organizational listening efforts to cope with a need to listen to thousands – sometimes hundreds of thousands – of publics and external stakeholders (p. 3).

The literature provides considerable support for the idea of an organizational listening architecture built around Macnamara’s requirements. For example, a number of business and organizational listening scholars have emphasized the importance of creating a *listening culture*, and they argue that success in creating and sustaining such a culture begins with and rests heavily on the commitment and involvement of senior leaders (Flynn, Valikoski, & Grau, 2008; Gregory, 2015; Murray, 2004).

Effectiveness in building a consumer listening culture also is closely connected to and driven by a firm’s *market and consumer orientation*. Both Jaworski and Kohli (1993) and Slater and Narver (1995) demonstrate that market and consumer orientation is key to an organization’s ability to sense and respond to consumers on a variety of fronts, including capturing and utilizing VoC-driven intelligence. Johnston and Reed (2017) have shown how an organizational listening environment can contribute to positive financial outcomes. Morgan et al. (2009) show that market and consumer orientation largely are manifested in the gathering, dissemination, and response to such VoC-driven intelligence. These activities, in turn, are positively associated with a firm’s performance capabilities and results. Taken together, all of the preceding studies emphasize the importance of organizations embracing norms, values, and policies that encourage market and consumer orientation and listening.

In addition to a strong consumer listening culture/orientation, success in capturing and leveraging the Voice of the Consumer also depends on effective listening *processes and practices*. As it pertains to organizational listening in a business context, Flynn et al. (2008)

assert that “it is imperative that management create an infrastructure in the organization that facilitates listening and feedback” (p. 146). Presumably, such an infrastructure would include organizational policies, systems, technologies, skills, resources, and other elements of the listening architecture similar to the ones proposed by Macnamara.

Without describing or recommending specific listening processes and mechanisms, Morgan, Anderson, and Mittal, (2005) suggest that four activities shape an organization's ability to capture and leverage the Voice of the Consumer: (a) data capture; (b) data analysis; (c) dissemination of findings and insights; and (d) utilization of these findings and insights. These authors go on to suggest that the preceding four activities are best implemented as part of a closed-loop system.

Taken together, these studies suggest that to develop, implement, and sustain an effective VoC program organizations must: (a) create the proper *climate* for consumer listening and learning through consumer-focused leadership, and through engaging organizational members (managers, employees, partners, etc.) in the listening/learning effort; and (b) build the necessary VoC *infrastructure* by implementing effective systems, processes and practices related to capturing the Voice of the Consumer, extracting and disseminating insights from it, and taking both consumer-specific and broad-based actions that are guided by and responsive to these insights.

Unfortunately, aside from a few proprietary studies by practitioners (Schmidt-Subramanian, 2014; Temkin, 2016), evidence of efforts to conduct a comprehensive study of VoC program effectiveness in relation to specific elements of organizational listening climate and infrastructure is scarce. For the most part, scholarly research in this area is yet to be undertaken. The present research project was aimed at addressing this gap.

The Present Research

To address the general issue of organizational practices and effectiveness in capturing and leveraging the Voice of the Consumer, a two-phased research project was conducted between 2015 and 2017, employing an exploratory sequential method (Creswell, 2015). The first phase was exploratory and qualitative, while the second phase was descriptive and quantitative. Because the project was primarily exploratory and descriptive in nature, both phases aimed at addressing research questions, rather than formulating and testing hypotheses.

Phase 1

The primary purpose of Phase 1 of this research was to identify organizational characteristics, processes, and practices that may be used to describe and evaluate the effectiveness of corporate Voice of the Consumer programs. Toward this end, two specific research questions were addressed:

RQ1: What are the processes and practices used by corporate organizations to create, support, and sustain a Voice of the Consumer program?

RQ2: What are the primary mechanisms, methods, practices, processes, systems, and technologies used by corporate organizations to capture, extract insights, disseminate insights, and utilize insights drawn from the Voice of the Consumer?

Method.

Listening is a multidimensional construct and research to date has produced a wide range of listening variables and measures (Worthington & Bodie, 2018). This includes considerable work to develop variables and measures of organizational listening (Cooper & Buchanan, 2003, 2010; Cooper & Husband, 1993; Cooper, Seibold, & Suchner, 1997). However, the bulk of these organizational listening variables/measures are internally-focused: They attempt to gauge

listening processes and competency in the context of communication *among* members of an organization *within* organizational boundaries. Most of these measures do not attempt, nor are they easily adapted, to describe or assess how effectively organizations listen to consumers and other *external* stakeholders.

Addressing RQ1 and RQ2, therefore, requires identifying and constructing an inventory of VoC program elements and characteristics. Creating such an inventory is largely a matter of compiling facts about “what” and “how” VoC programs are built and managed, which fundamentally is an exploratory, qualitative research task (Silverman, 2001, 2005).

Research by Griffin and Hauser (1993) and Hauser (2007) was instructive in planning Phase 1 of this project. Their findings suggest that exploratory, qualitative research aimed at generating a comprehensive inventory of marketing or managerial elements often can be accomplished via 20-30 depth interviews. For example, in the case of the study conducted by Griffin and Hauser (1993), of the total number of non-redundant consumer needs that were identified via exploratory qualitative research, 90% of those needs were identified after just 10 interviews, and 99% were identified after just 20.

Accordingly, in planning Phase 1 of this project we chose to conduct depth interviews with individuals who were highly knowledgeable about the VoC programs in their respective organizations, using a guided, semi-structured approach (Eriksson & Kovalainen, 2008). Twenty-five (25) depth interviews were conducted with managers and employees, none of whom was affiliated with the same organization. These individuals were screened and selected to meet *one* of the following qualifications:

1. The individual was an *executive sponsor* of his/her organization’s VoC program;
2. The individual was the *VoC program director* or team leader;

3. The individual was a VoC program *team member*; or
4. The individual was an organizational member/manager who *receives and uses* VoC-based information and insights.

Interview invitations were accepted by (and interviews were conducted with) seven executive sponsors, three program directors, nine team members, and six VoC information recipients/users.

The depth interviews focused on generating details and identifying specific processes and practices regarding two basic questions: (a) *how an organization builds and sustains a climate for consumer listening*, and (b) *how an organization goes about capturing, analyzing, disseminating, and using VoC data*. To ensure consistency of the interview method, the principal researcher (this author) conducted all 25 interviews. These interviews were conducted via telephone and ranged from 45 minutes to 1 hour. Each interview was recorded and subsequently transcribed for further analysis.

Analysis.

Analysis of the data obtained from depth interviews was performed by three individuals who were employees of a marketing research firm specializing in the design and management of corporate VoC programs. These individuals volunteered to assist with Phase 1 of the project in anticipation of acquiring additional analytical skills and experience that would be beneficial to their long-term professional/career growth and development.

From interview transcripts, the principal researcher produced VoC process/practice descriptions. Each description was a verbatim answer to a “what” or “how” question: It was a declarative statement of how an interviewee’s respective organization went about addressing the two basic questions outlined above. For example, regarding building a climate for consumer

listening, one interviewee said, “Each quarter, our Chief Customer Experience Officer leads an all-company meeting to review survey results.” Examples of descriptions of consumer listening and learning practices include statements like “We record all calls received by our Customer Care Center,” and “We use text analytics to identify key positive and negative aspects of the consumer experience.”

All VoC process/practice descriptions were transferred to individual index cards, one card for each description. Three such sets of these cards were produced and used by the team of analysts to sort and classify process/practice descriptions. The end goal was to create an inventory having primary categories, each of which included secondary-level components – in essence, to construct an elementary taxonomy of VoC characteristics and practices.

The 25 depth interviews ultimately produced a total of 170 descriptions of individual VoC program elements (before sorting). Results, illustrated in Figure 1, indicate that approximately 90% of these were identified from the first 14 interviews, which basically is consistent with the results reported by Griffin and Hauser (1993) and Hauser (2007).

--- Figure 1 about here ---

Prior to analyzing all of the data, a test of inter-analyst agreement was conducted using data from the first 3 interviews, which yielded 64 descriptions of VoC program elements (before sorting). Each analyst independently sorted what s/he deemed to be non-redundant VoC program elements into distinct groups. Redundant elements were placed in a common group. The test of inter-analyst agreement focused on the degree to which each pair of analysts sorted the 64 elements similarly (or not). Cohen’s kappa (κ) was computed for each pair of analysts (Cohen, 1960), and the mean κ among the three pairs was .82, which is considered to be a “very good” level of agreement (Altman, 1990; Landis & Koch, 1977). Thus, it was concluded that the

sorting procedure employed by the three analysts was reliable and could be used for all depth interview data.

The three analysts independently sorted all 170 elements (process/practice descriptions) into separate groups. Each group was thought to represent a distinct VoC program aspect or characteristic (primary category). Once these primary categories were created, elements within a given primary category were sorted once again: Each analyst sorted what s/he deemed to be non-redundant elements into distinct sub-groups. Redundant elements were placed in a common sub-group.

As a final step in the process, the analysts met as a face-to-face group to compare their individual primary and secondary groupings. Differences were discussed and consensus was sought/achieved regarding how to reconcile each. Once all differences were reconciled and a consensus-based taxonomy was produced, the principal researcher and analytical team discussed and reached consensus regarding: (a) how to describe/label each primary category; and (b) wording of the items within each primary category. Once such consensus was achieved, the Phase 1 analysis process was complete.

Results

The analysis of depth interview data reduced the original 170 VoC program characteristics and practices to 58. Each of these 58 elements, in turn, was grouped under one of the 10 primary categories, which were labeled as follows:

1. Senior Sponsorship and Support of the VoC Program
2. Organizational Engagement and Buy-in with regard to the VoC Program
3. Methods and Mechanisms of Consumer Listening
4. Consumer Experience Metrics and Targets

5. Analysis and Integration of VoC Data
6. Access to and Dissemination of VoC Data and Insights
7. Use of VoC to Respond to and Manage Individual Consumer Relationships
8. Use of VoC to Train and Develop Managers, Employees, and Partners
9. Use of the VoC to Drive Systemic Improvement
10. VoC Program Sustainability

Each of the above primary categories, along with the detailed characteristics and practices grouped under it, are displayed in Table 1.

--- Table 1 about here ---

RQ1 centers on the *processes and practices used by companies to create, support, and sustain a VoC program.*

Phase 1 results suggest that three of the primary categories (1, 2, and 10) relate to this question, subsuming 17 of the individual characteristics and practices. These findings suggest that senior sponsorship and support, organizational buy-in, and efforts to sustain and refine the VoC program are keys to creating and maintaining the necessary organizational climate for consumer listening.

RQ2 centers on the *methods and mechanisms used by corporate organizations to capture, extract insights, disseminate insights, and utilize insights drawn from the Voice of the Consumer.*

Phase 1 results suggest that the remaining seven categories (3-9) relate to this question, subsuming the 41 remaining individual characteristics/practices. These findings suggest that multiple listening mechanisms, methods of data analysis and integration, processes for disseminating VoC-based insights, and processes for using these insights to support

organizational decisions and actions are keys to creating and maintaining the necessary organizational infrastructure for consumer listening.

The results of Phase 1 appear to reflect and provide support for the relevance of many requirements of an organizational architecture of listening proposed by Macnamara (2018). The results also appear to reflect and provide support for the four-step process of VoC data capture, analysis, dissemination, and utilization proposed by Morgan et al. (2005). However, at this point in the project, the question of how well these elements have been incorporated or deployed in corporate VoC programs, along with questions about VoC program effectiveness, remained unanswered. Phase 2 aimed at addressing this gap.

Phase 2

The primary purpose of Phase 2 of this research was to assess the current effectiveness of corporate Voice of the Consumer programs. Toward this end, the following research questions were addressed:

- RQ3: What methods and mechanisms are used by corporate organizations to listen to and capture feedback from their consumers?
- RQ4: Overall, how effective are corporate VoC programs with respect to meeting program goals and objectives?
- RQ5: How effective are corporate VoC programs with respect to the 58 specific characteristics and practices in the 10 primary areas identified in Phase 1 of this project?

Method

One concern that surfaced during project design was the issue of organizational heterogeneity. Governmental, educational, and non-profit organizations differ from commercial,

for-profit organizations in important ways, including organizational mission and goals, management and governance, operations, relevant publics and stakeholders, and as Macnamara (2016) has discussed, listening priorities and approaches. Additionally, even among commercial organizations, companies that sell to consumers differ from those that sell to other businesses. While all types of organizations can and should be studied with respect to their approaches to and effectiveness at listening to consumers and other external stakeholders, for the purpose of this project, a decision was made to try to minimize the impact of organizational heterogeneity by narrowing the focus to business-to-consumer (B2C) firms.

Accordingly, Phase 2 consisted of an online survey of 309 business-to-consumer (B2C) organizations, representing multiple sectors and categories of goods and services. These firms were among 1000 that were invited to complete the survey. The sampling source was obtained from a company that specializes in providing names and contact information (email addresses) for managers and employees who work in B2C companies. No attempt was made to set quotas for any given sector or industry.

The industries and sectors that were represented among survey respondents included airlines, hospitality, telecommunication, entertainment, automotive, retail banking, consumer packaged goods, property/casualty insurance, quick service restaurants, casual dining restaurants, healthcare and pharmaceuticals, cellular and satellite services, and consumer electronics. No single sector comprised more than 15 percent of the total sample, and most comprised between 5 and 9 percent.

Survey respondents were screened to ensure they met the same qualifications as individuals who participated in Phase 1. That is, each respondent had to be knowledgeable about the VoC program in his/her organization because s/he was either: (a) the executive sponsor of the

program; (b) the program director or team leader; (c) a program team member; or (d) a manager or employee who receives and utilizes VoC data and insights. As Table 2 illustrates, the proportion of total respondents matching one of the above qualifications was roughly the same for each of the four qualifications.

--- Table 2 about here ---

The survey asked respondents to describe the different methods used in their respective organizations to capture Voice of the Consumer data. Respondents also were asked to rate the overall success of their respective VoC programs in: (a) achieving program goals and objectives; (b) helping the company improve consumer experience and satisfaction; and (c) helping the company improve consumer loyalty, retention, and repeat business. The items and rating scale used to measure overall program effectiveness is shown in Figure 2. Cronbach's α (Nunnally, 1978) was .899 for the three measures, indicating a high degree of reliability.

--- Figure 2 about here ---

Respondents also were asked to report the extent to which the specific processes and practices shown in Table 1 have been fully implemented within their respective organizations. An example of the items and rating scale used to measure implementation of specific VoC program characteristics and practices in the area of "Senior Sponsorship and Support" is shown in Figure 3. This same rating scale was applied in measuring implementation of specific VoC program characteristics and practices in all ten primary categories developed during Phase 1.

--- Figure 3 about here ---

Prior to data analysis, ratings of implementation effectiveness regarding specific VoC program characteristics and practices in all ten primary categories were re-scaled using a percent-of-maximum-possible or POMP method (Cohen, Aiken, & West, 1999). For each of the

10 primary VoC categories, a respondent's observed scores on all items associated with a given category were summed. This sum was then divided by the maximum possible and multiplied by 100. The result was a new summary score for each category having a range of 0 to 100.

Reliability estimates (see Table 5) were very high for all categories, with Cronbach's α ranging from .82 (Using the VoC to Respond to Individual Consumers) to .95 (Using the VoC to Drive Systemic Improvement).

Finally, in addition to the measures described above, the survey captured demographic and firmographic data. However, these data are not discussed further in this paper, as they were not used to produce any of the results of Phase 2 reported below.

Analysis and results

RQ3 centers on the *number and types of methods and mechanisms used by corporate organizations to listen to and capture feedback from their consumers.*

Results reveal that most organizations use more than one method to capture the Voice of the Consumer, and that *a majority of firms (84%) use between 3 and 6 different methods.*

Detailed results pertaining to usage of specific listening mechanisms and methods are summarized in Table 3. Transactional and cumulative experience *surveys* are the most commonly used approaches, but more than half of all organizations listen and learn via *consumer emails, social media, feedback from consumer-facing employees, inbound consumer calls, and/or focus groups or depth interviews with consumers.*

---Table 3 about here ---

RQ4 centers on *overall VoC program effectiveness.*

Results, summarized in Table 4, reveal that approximately one-third (33%) of the respondents characterized their organization's VoC program as "very successful" with respect to

meeting its goals and objectives. The same percentage characterized their VoC program as “very successful” in helping the company improve consumer experiences and relationships. However, only 27% said their program was “very successful” in helping the company improve consumer loyalty, retention, and repeat business. Furthermore, on all three measures, most respondents characterized their programs as either “somewhat successful” or “not very successful.” Thus, results of Phase 2 suggest that *most organizations are not yet where they want to be when it comes to overall VoC program effectiveness*. An examination of results pertaining to RQ5 provides some insights as to why.

---Table 4 about here ---

RQ5 centers on *VoC program effectiveness with respect to the 58 specific characteristics and practices in the 10 primary areas identified in Phase 1 of this project*.

A one-way, repeated measures analysis of variance (Keppel, 1982) was performed on the primary category scores. Results reveal that at least some means among the ten categories differ significantly ($F = 6.72, df = 9, 300, p < .05$). Post-hoc comparisons among means were conducted using the Bonferroni procedure (Kirk, 1982).

Table 5 displays mean scores for each of the 10 primary VoC categories in descending order from highest to lowest. Significantly different pairs among all means also are displayed in Table 5. These results suggest that respondents perceive their VoC programs have been *most effective* when it comes to:

1. Securing senior-level sponsorship and support of the VoC program and consumer listening efforts;
2. Getting manager and employees to buy into and engage in consumer listening efforts;

3. Implementing multiple mechanisms and methods of consumer listening; and
4. Using data and insights drawn from the Voice of the Consumer to respond to and manage relationships with individual consumers

--- Table 5 about here ---

Mean scores on all other categories fall below the mid-point of the scale (50.0), and respondents perceive their VoC programs have been *least effective* when it comes to:

1. Data Analysis and Integration;
2. Access to and Dissemination of VoC Data and Insights;
3. Use of the VoC to Train/Develop Managers and Employees;
4. Use of VoC to Drive Systemic Improvement; and
5. Sustainability

As Table 5 illustrates, all of the mean scores in the four areas in which VoC programs are most effective differ significantly from all of the mean scores in the five areas in which such programs are least effective.

A closer look at individual items regarding specific VoC program characteristics and practices reinforces the preceding observations regarding areas of relative effectiveness or ineffectiveness. Table 6 displays the twelve items for which mean ratings are highest among all measures of VoC program characteristics and practices. Four of these items related to how the organization creates a climate for consumer listening (through leadership, organizational engagement, and priorities). Three of these items reflect how organizations capture VoC data. The other five items center on how the organization uses VoC data to respond to and manage individual consumer relationships.

--- Table 6 about here ---

By way of contrast, Table 7 displays the twelve items for which mean ratings are lowest among all measures of VoC program characteristics and practices. Five of these items relate to how organizations analyze and integrate VoC data. Four of these items relate to the use of VoC-driven insights to drive systemic improvement. The other three items focus on practices designed to sustain and reinforce the importance of listening and responding to consumers.

--- Table 7 about here ---

Taken together, the results pertaining to RQ5 indicate that organizations have been relatively successful in *creating a climate* for consumer listening, and at *capturing VoC data*. Also, these organizations have been relatively successful at using VoC data to *respond to and manage relationships with individual consumers*. In contrast, organizations have not been as successful at *integrating, analyzing, and disseminating* VoC data, nor have they been highly effective at *utilizing* VoC data and metrics *to develop managers and employees or to drive systemic improvement*. These organizations also have not been very successful at implementing processes and practices to *sustain* the VoC program itself.

Discussion

In 2008, Flynn and coauthors bemoaned the fact that “empirical research into listening as an organizational variable appears to be almost non-existent in the scholarly business and management literature” (p. 147). A decade later Macnamara (2018) declared that “the findings of a literature review revealing little attention to listening in organizational, corporate, government, and political communication and related fields of practice such as public relations” served as the impetus for his three-year Organizational Listening Project (pp. 3-4). Fortunately, Macnamara’s work, along with that of a handful of other scholars (e.g., Johnston & Reed, 2017; Kluger &

Zaidel, 2013; Maben & Gearhart, 2018; Purdy & Manning, 2015) has produced a burgeoning and steadily growing literature on organizational listening research.

The present research project aimed at contributing to this corpus of research by exploring how (and how effectively) companies capture and leverage the Voice of the Consumer. Results show that many organizations work hard to build a climate for consumer listening, and that these organizations are using a variety of mechanisms to capture consumer feedback. However, the results also reveal that most organizations are not yet where they want to be with regard to VoC overall program effectiveness, and that this most likely is because they are falling short in the areas of analysis, dissemination, and utilization of VoC-driven data and insights.

Findings from this research have implications for theory and knowledge development, implications for practitioners, and several directions for future research. These are discussed below.

Implications for Organizational Communication Theory and Knowledge Development

The results of the present research have clear implications for continuing development and empirical support of current organizational communication theory. For example, a theoretical framework proposed by McPhee and Zaug (2000) asserts that the “communicative constitution of organizations” requires four types of message flows and interactions: (a) Membership Negotiation – determining who and how individuals become members of an organization; (b) Self-Structuring – defining member roles, responsibilities, authority, etc.; (c) Activity Coordination – aligning people, resources, and work processes to produce necessary and/or desirable organizational outcomes; and Institutional Positioning – establishing and managing relationships with external publics, stakeholders, and partners. McPhee and Zaug (2000) argue that, although they are “analytically distinct,” a single interaction or message can

“address more than one constitutive task,” and that “complex organizations exist only in the relatedness of these four types of flow” (p. 1).

Phase 1 results show that, in many corporate organizations, considerable self-structuring and activity coordination are aimed at establishing a climate and infrastructure for consumer listening. However, Phase 2 results suggest that, when it comes to managing relationships with consumers, current VoC programs may be only partially effective. That is, to the extent that they are not “helping the company improve customer experiences and relationships,” VoC programs may not sufficiently support institutional positioning objectives. Intersection of the preceding three flows, therefore, probably is both necessary and inevitable if VoC programs are to be successful in fulfilling their ultimate goals. Future research should explore how such intersection occurs and is sequenced. For example, does consumer feedback initially inform (directly or tacitly) how companies should organize people and activity to deliver improved products, services, and consumer experiences? Does the messaging about activity coordination then influence organizational self-structuring, and perhaps even membership negotiation (based on the types of individuals and skill sets required to achieve consumer-centric alignment of people and activities)? Questions regarding communication content, networking, and organizational transformation in relation to the intersection of the four flows – and in the context of VoC program management – also should be examined.

Implications for Listening Theory and Knowledge Development

By introducing and explicating concepts such as the “seven canons of listening” and an “architecture of listening,” Macnamara (2016, 2018) has identified some of the critical elements upon which organizational listening theory can be founded and related scholarly research driven. However, such theory is in a very early stage of development. It is very likely that additional

factors must be identified and understood to achieve the vision of a mature and robust theory and practice of organizational listening.

Results of the present research project may contribute to listening theory and knowledge development in at least three ways. First, by exploring corporate efforts to capture and leverage the Voice of the Consumer, this research hopefully has raised awareness and understanding of this type of organizational listening. More importantly, additional research on VoC program characteristics, practices, and effectiveness should reveal the extent to which this form of organizational listening is similar to – and different from – other forms. Such research, in turn, has a potential to facilitate construction of typologies and/or taxonomies based on organizational listening *contexts and classes*. Organizational listening models and frameworks may develop as insights drawn from these classification systems are integrated with information regarding other factors known to influence organizational listening practices, such as differences in organizational types (governmental, corporate, educational, not-for-profit, etc.).

Speaking of differences in organizational types, for reasons discussed earlier in the paper, only B2C companies were surveyed in the present study, and the decision to narrow the focus in this manner probably had a hand in shaping at least some of the key findings. A study of business-to-business (B2B) firms might well reveal a different “state” of VoC program effectiveness and maturity. It might also reveal that different processes, methods, and practices are in play in B2B settings. Future research should address the preceding questions. Also, research on VoC program practices and effectiveness in governmental, educational, not-for-profit, and other types of organizations should be undertaken. Such studies will provide essential insights regarding the ways in which VoC listening processes and practices may be comparable across different industrial and organizational settings, as well as where there are critical

differences.

Finally, while an attempt was made to control for industrial and market heterogeneity in the present research, the same cannot be said for respondent heterogeneity. Recall that survey respondents could be/were either VoC executive sponsors, VoC program leaders or team members, or recipients/users of learning drawn from VoC data. Data from all of these respondents were aggregated for the purpose of survey data analysis. It is possible that differences in roles and responsibilities could influence respondents' knowledge and understanding of different aspects of their respective VoC programs. This, in turn, might produce differences in perceived program strengths and weaknesses among role-based sub-groups. In the present research, sample size limitations made it impractical to conduct meaningful statistical comparisons of survey responses among sub-groups defined by the above roles/responsibilities (especially in light of the number of measures that would need to have been compared). Still, the potential for role-based influences on/differences in perceptions of VoC program effectiveness cannot be ruled out, and these also need to be addressed in future studies. An understanding of the presence and magnitude of such role-based influences and differences will enable scholars to make informed decisions regarding whether and how to integrate them into organizational listening theory, research, and practice.

Practical Implications

Survey results have practical implications for the design and management of VoC programs on at least three fronts: (a) data analysis and integration, (b) dissemination of VoC data and insights; and (c) data utilization.

Two points regarding how different types of VoC data (and methods used to capture these data) *may actually inhibit effective analysis and integration* are noteworthy. First, a

combination of structured and unstructured data appears to be in play in most organizations. Such a combination furnishes a rich mix, but also has the potential to make data integration and analysis increasingly challenging due to data incompatibility. The issue essentially boils down to a problem of trying to compare “apples and oranges.” For example, if survey ratings utilize one set of categories/sub-categories, but consumer comments are organized using a different set, it may be very difficult – if not impossible – to align and compare these two data sources. The problem compounds with increases in the number of data sources.

A second and related point centers on the source, flow, and sequencing of information being captured via different methods. In the case of surveys, focus groups, and depth interviews, companies reach out to and solicit feedback from consumers. Conversely, in the case of emails and inbound calls, consumers initiate communication and contact with the organization. Communication via social media and/or from consumer-facing employees can be either company-initiated or consumer initiated. These differences in the communication sources, flow, and sequencing have the potential to influence data content and structure, and thus also may contribute to data incompatibility.

The above two points may help explain why many organizations have not been as effective at VoC data analysis and integration as they would like. Survey findings related to effectiveness in implementing specific VoC practices reinforce this point. For example, the mean rating (44.5) on “Data from all sources are organized and analyzed using a standard set of categories” falls in the bottom third of all ratings. Lacking such uniform categories, many organizations may not have created a data management approach that enables different data sources to “work together.”

Another point centers on several findings that reinforce Macnamara's (2018) claims about the challenges of organizational listening:

1. Reliance on a mix of surveys, emails, social media, and inbound consumer calls reflects the need to *scale up* the organizational listening effort.
2. Consumer listening performed via most of the most commonly-used methods is *mediated*.
3. Many of these methods require listening and data capture efforts to be *delegated* to individuals and departments (e.g., surveys, focus groups, and depth interviews probably are delegated to a marketing research department or partner).
4. With the exception of consumer calls, focus groups, or depth interviews with consumers, listening via other channels and methods is *asynchronous* – it does not happen in real time among interactants, but rather, it occurs across time and space.

Thus, in addition to contributing to data incompatibility, variations in timing, location, and ownership of data collection also may make *dissemination* of VoC data and insights increasingly challenging. Again, survey findings related to effectiveness in implementing specific VoC practices reinforce this point. For example, the mean rating (44.1) on “Managers and employees can access data from all VoC sources on-demand, and in real time” falls in the bottom third of all ratings. Lacking a platform for housing and making all data available at a single point, many organizations have not created an infrastructure that facilitates high-speed VoC data access and dissemination.

The implication for VoC program managers is that steps must be taken to maximize data compatibility and accessibility. Use of a standard taxonomy to organize and analyze all VoC

data, along with technology that enables real-time access to up-to-the-minute data from any source, are examples of steps that can be taken to improve data compatibility and accessibility.

Results regarding effectiveness at *data utilization* also have implications for VoC program managers and users. On one hand, organizations appear to be relatively effective at using VoC-driven information to respond to and manage relationships with individual consumers. On the other hand, these organizations have not been as successful at using such information to develop their managers and employees, or to drive broad-based, systemic improvements in internal operations and/or consumer experiences.

The implication for VoC program managers is that efforts to improve utilization on the latter two fronts must be undertaken. VoC-driven insights should be incorporated in human resources training materials and mentoring programs, particularly those designed for customer facing personnel (Goodman, 2009). Such insights also should be used to focus and direct efforts that employ Six Sigma or similar process and performance improvement techniques (Pande, Neuman, & Cavanagh, 2000; Pyzdek & Keller, 2010).

Conclusion

The growth in interest and inquiry into organizational listening is an exciting and promising development. The present research project focused on how (and how effectively) corporate organizations capture and leverage the Voice of the Consumer. Results indicate that progress has been made with respect to this particular form of organizational listening, but that considerable opportunities for improvement still remain. The findings also raise a variety of research questions that need to be addressed. Many answers and insights – along with their implications for organizational communication and listening theory, research, and practice – most likely have yet to be realized.

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Table 1: VoC Program Categories and Associated Processes/Practices

1. Senior Sponsorship and Support

One or more senior leaders sponsor and “own” our VoC program.

Consumer experience, and the way we listen and learn about consumer experience, are top priorities in my organization.

Senior leaders regularly and visibly reinforce the importance of consumer experience, and the way we listen and learn about it.

The company commits the necessary financial resources to support our VoC program.

The company commits the necessary human resources to support our VoC program.

Senior leaders regularly review our VoC Program, along with the status and progress of efforts to improve it.

2. Organizational Engagement and Buy-In

Managers and employees in all parts of the organization buy-in to the importance of listening to the VoC.

Managers and employees in all parts of the organization see great value in our VoC Program.

Managers and employees in all departments regularly and frequently review results and insights drawn from the VoC.

Cross-functional teams regularly and frequently review results and insights drawn from the VoC.

A centralized team oversees our VoC program, and provides ongoing support to managers and employees who see and use VoC results and insights.

3. Methods and Mechanisms of Consumer Listening

We are able to collect enough data to get a clear understanding of the total consumer experience.

Our VoC program includes feedback we collect, as well as feedback consumers furnish without being asked to do so.

Our VoC program includes both structured (e.g., survey ratings) and unstructured (e.g., open-ended comments) data.

All data about the consumer experience are collected regularly and frequently.

We enable consumers to provide their feedback through many different channels and methods.

Table 1: VoC Program Categories and Associated Processes/Practices (continued)

4. Metrics and Targets

Core consumer metrics (e.g., overall satisfaction) are collected and included as part of a corporate scorecard or dashboard.

Measures are gathered regarding how consumers evaluate specific aspects of their experiences, and these measures are used to determine key strengths and opportunities for improvement.

There is a formal process for setting targets for consumer metrics that is easy for employees and managers to explain.

Scores on consumer metrics are evaluated based on whether they are improving and/or remaining at high levels of performance.

Scores on consumer metrics are evaluated based on how they compare to key competitors and/or industry norms and benchmarks.

5. Data Analysis and Integration

Data from all VoC sources are organized and analyzed using a standard set of categories.

We use one or more formal methods to determine which aspects of the consumer experience have the greatest impact on NPS® and/or other key outcomes.

We use a formal method to integrate data from all VoC sources to identify where we are performing well, and where there are opportunities for improvement.

We perform analyses that show how consumer metrics are related to key internal operational metrics.

We perform analyses that show how consumer metrics are related to key business outcomes, such as consumer retention and share-of-wallet.

We use text analytics to get maximum insight from all consumer statements and comments.

All of the above analyses are performed at an overall company level, as well as key divisions and departments.

Table 1: VoC Program Categories and Associated Processes/Practices (continued)

6. Access to and Dissemination of VoC Data and Insights

Senior leaders regularly present results and insights drawn from the VoC at all-company and team meetings and events.

Each department in our organization regularly reviews results and insights drawn from the VoC that are specific to that department or area.

A technology or platform makes data, results, and insights drawn from the VoC accessible to all departments and teams.

Results for all consumer experience measures and consumer comments are displayed using a consistent format or dashboard.

Managers and employees can access VoC data from various sources on-demand, and in real time.

Managers and employees can conduct their own analyses of VoC data using tools available via a technology/platform.

7. Use of the VoC to Respond to and Manage Relationships with Individual Consumers

A contact center is in place to respond to individual consumers who call with questions, requests, or problems.

An individual, department, or unit is in place to respond to individual consumers who email with questions, requests, or problems.

An individual, department, or unit is in place to respond to individual consumers who post questions, requests, or complaints at the company website.

“Hot alerts” from consumer surveys are used to follow-up with dissatisfied consumers.

Our organization follows-up with and attempts to resolve the dissatisfaction of consumers who post negative messages about the company on social media.

Highly satisfied consumers are encouraged to talk about their experiences by posting messages about the company on social media.

Table 1: VoC Program Categories and Associated Processes/Practices (continued)

8. Use of the VoC to Train and Develop Managers, Employees, and Partners

Results and insights drawn from the VoC are used in the training of managers and employees who are expected to use these results and insights to improve business processes and operations.

Results and insights drawn from the VoC are used to coach and mentor managers and employees who have direct contact with consumers.

Consumer metrics and results are used to set performance goals for managers and employees who have direct contact with consumers.

Results and insights drawn from the VoC are used to identify top performers among managers and employees who have direct contact with consumers.

Results and insights drawn from the VoC are used to empower managers and employees who have direct contact with consumers.

Results and insights drawn from the VoC are used to identify opportunities to give managers and employees who have direct contact with consumers better tools and resources.

9. Use of the VoC to Drive Systemic Improvement

We use a formal process to establish accountability for and ownership of priorities for improvement and action drawn from the VoC.

Owners of these priorities form teams that are tasked with developing and implementing action plans.

These teams use a formal process to ensure they thoroughly understand the consumer experience issue that has been given top priority before they begin to develop action plans.

These teams use a formal process to identify root causes of poor or dissatisfactory consumer experiences.

These teams use a formal process to generate and evaluate potential actions and solutions to be included in action plans.

These teams regularly monitor relevant consumer metrics and data, and provide progress updates once action plans have been implemented.

Table 1: VoC Program Categories and Associated Processes/Practices (continued)

10. VoC Program Sustainability

The compensation of senior leaders who sponsor and own the VoC is tied to actual consumer experience results and improvements.

The compensation of managers and employees who have direct contact with consumers is tied to actual consumer experience results and improvements.

Our organization recognizes and rewards top performers for achieving or surpassing performance goals that are based on consumer experience metrics and results.

Our organization formally celebrates successful improvement efforts as reflected by consumer experience metrics and related results.

Senior leaders plan to continue or increase funding of our VoC program.

Efforts are made periodically to identify specific ways to improve our VoC program.

Table 2: Survey Sample Composition Based on VoC Program Roles and Responsibilities

<i>VoC Program Role/Responsibility</i>	<i>Percent of Total Sample</i>
Executive sponsor	27%
Program Director/Team Leader	20%
Program Team Member	22%
Recipient/User of VoC Data & Insights	21%

Base = 309 Respondents

Table 3: Types and Incidence of Methods Used to Capture the Voice of the Consumer

<i>Method</i>	<i>Percent*</i>
Transactional/Event-Driven Surveys	62%
Relationship/Cumulative Experience Surveys	60%
Consumer Emails	60%
Feedback from Consumer-Facing Employees	56%
Inbound Consumer Calls	56%
Focus Groups/Depth Interviews	53%
Consumer Feedback Posted on Company Website	48%
Social Media	44%
Benchmarking Surveys	43%
Consumer Advisory Groups	37%
Feedback from Consumer-Facing Channel Partners	33%
Ethnographic/Observational Studies	14%
Mystery Shopping	9%
Consumer Comment Cards	3%

* Percentage of respondents who report using this method in their organization

Table 4: Respondents' Evaluation of Overall VoC Program Effectiveness

Question: "Overall, how effective has your organization's Voice of the Consumer program been when it comes to *meeting its goals and objectives*?"

<i>Response</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Very Successful	33%
Somewhat Successful	50%
Not Very Successful	17%

Question: "Overall, how effective has your organization's Voice of the Consumer program been when it comes to *helping the company improve consumer experiences and satisfaction*?"

<i>Response</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Very Successful	33%
Somewhat Successful	45%
Not Very Successful	22%

Question: "Overall, how effective has your organization's Voice of the Consumer program been when it comes to *helping the company improve consumer loyalty, retention, and repeat business*?"

<i>Response</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Very Successful	27%
Somewhat Successful	40%
Not Very Successful	33%

Base: 309 Respondents

Table 5: Mean Scores and Reliability Estimates for Ten Primary VoC Program Categories

<i>Category</i>	<i>Mean*</i>	<i>α**</i>
Use of the VoC to Respond to and Manage Relationships with Individual Consumers	60.3 _{ABCDE}	.828
Methods and Mechanisms of Consumer Listening	57.3 _{FGHIJ}	.893
Senior Sponsorship and Support	54.3 _{KLMNO}	.918
Organizational Buy-In and Engagement	54.1 _{PQRST}	.916
Targets and Metrics	48.1	.922
Sustainability	45.2 _{AFKP}	.920
Access to and Dissemination of VoC Data and Insights	44.7 _{BGLQ}	.926
Use of the VoC to Train/Develop Managers and Employees	44.4 _{CHMR}	.941
Data Analysis and Integration	43.1 _{DINS}	.939
Use of VoC to Drive Systemic Improvement	41.4 _{EJOT}	.955

Base: 309 Respondents

* Means having a common letter in the subscript differ significantly at or beyond the .05 level of confidence (two-tailed). Means can range from a possible minimum of 0 and a possible maximum of 100.

** Cronbach's Alpha

Table 6: Mean Scores for “Top Twelve” VoC Program Characteristics and Practices Items

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Our VoC program includes both structured (e.g. survey ratings) and unstructured (e.g., consumer comments) data.	71.6
A contact center is in place to respond to individual consumers who call with questions, requests, or problems.	69.4
An individual, department, or unit is in place to respond to consumers who email with questions, requests, or problems.	67.4
“Hot alerts” from consumer surveys are used to follow-up with dissatisfied consumers.	62.1
An individual, department, or unit is in place to respond to consumers who post questions, requests, or complaints on the company’s website.	60.6
Our organization follows-up with and attempts to resolve the dissatisfaction of consumers who post negative messages about the company on social media.	59.0
Consumer experience, and the way we listen and learn about consumer experience, are top priorities in my organization.	58.3
One or more senior leaders sponsor and “own” our VoC program.	58.1
Measures are gathered regarding how consumers evaluate specific aspects of their experiences, and these measures are used to determine strengths and opportunities for improvement.	55.5
All data about consumer experience are collected regularly and frequently.	55.5
Senior leaders regularly and visibly reinforce the importance of consumer experience, and the way we listen and learn about it.	54.8
A centralized team oversees our VoC program, and provides ongoing support to managers and employees who see and use VoC results and insights.	54.2

Base: 309 Respondents

Table 7: Mean Scores for “Bottom Twelve” VoC Program Characteristics and Practices Items

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>
The compensation of senior leaders who sponsor and own the VoC program is tied to actual consumer experience results and improvements.	35.0
Improvement teams use a formal process to generate and evaluate potential actions and solutions to be included in consumer experience improvement plans.	37.8
We use text analytics to get maximum insight from all consumer statements and comments.	38.5
We use a formal process to establish accountability for and ownership of priorities for action and improvement based on VoC-driven insights.	39.1
The compensation of managers and employees who have direct contact with consumers is tied to actual consumer experience results and improvements.	39.4
We perform analyses that show how consumer metrics are related to key business outcomes, such as consumer retention and share-of-wallet.	39.4
Scores on consumer metrics are evaluated based on how they compare to key competitors and/or industry norms and benchmarks.	39.5
Our organization recognizes and rewards top performers for achieving or surpassing performance goals that are based on consumer experience metrics and results.	40.3
We use a formal method to integrate data from all VoC sources to determine where we are performing well, and where there are opportunities for improvement.	40.5
We perform analyses that show how consumer metrics are related to key internal operational metrics.	41.5
Improvement teams use a formal process to ensure they thoroughly understand a VoC-driven issue that has been high priority before they begin to develop action plans.	41.6
Improvement teams use a formal process to identify root causes of poor or dissatisfactory consumer experiences.	41.9

Base: 309 Respondents

Figure 1: Cumulative Identification of VoC Program Elements via Depth Interviews

Figure 2: Measuring Overall VoC Program Effectiveness

Overall, how successful has your organization's Voice of the Consumer (VoC) program been when it comes to *meeting its goals and objectives*?

- Not Very Successful
- Somewhat Successful
- Very Successful

Overall, how successful has your organization's Voice of the Consumer (VoC) program been when it comes to *helping the company improve consumer experiences and satisfaction*?

- Not Very Successful
- Somewhat Successful
- Very Successful

Overall, how successful has your organization's Voice of the Consumer (VoC) program been when it comes to *helping the company improve consumer loyalty, retention, and repeat business*?

- Not Very Successful
- Somewhat Successful
- Very Successful

Figure 3: Example of a Measure of VoC Program Practices Implementation in the Area of “Senior Sponsorship and Support”

Senior Sponsorship & Support	This Does NOT Describe What Goes on in My Organization		This is Partially Accurate in Describing What Goes on in My Organization		This Very Accurately Describes What Goes on in My Organization
One or more senior leaders sponsor and “own” our VoC program. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consumer experience, and the way we listen and learn about consumer experience, are top priorities in my organization. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Senior leaders regularly and visibly reinforce the importance of consumer experience, and the way we listen and learn about it. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The company commits the necessary financial resources to support our VoC program. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The company commits the necessary human resources to support our VoC program. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Senior leaders regularly review our VoC Program, along with the status and progress of efforts to improve it. (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>